

Commercial orbital constellations of small spacecraft used for agriculture

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Temporal data coverage: 2016 – 2025

Name: name of satellite constellation

Resolution: spatial resolution

Bands: M – multispectral; H – hyperspectral; T – thermal; V – video; X, C, L – SAR bands.

Number: number of satellites in constellation (current and planned).

Company: constellation operator.

Country: the country where the constellation operator is registered.

Year: first year of constellation deployment.

The table contains data as of October 1, 2023.

Satellite constellation was included in the table, if its application for agriculture and similar tasks was declared by the company-operator.

All satellite constellations for which data were found assumed a revisit time of less than 1 day. Therefore, the revisit time is not shown in the table.

Data on Chinese satellite constellations are usually given for the only known satellite in the constellation.

The launch of the demonstrator satellite was considered the beginning of the constellation deployment.

For SAR satellites, the ground-based spatial resolution in Stripmap mode is given.

Hyperlinks point to sources of information.

Name	Resolution, m	Bands	Number	Company	Country	Year
Flock	3,7	M	424	Planet Labs	USA	2014
SkySat	0,9 – 2 ¹	M	21	Planet Labs	USA	2013
Jilin-1 Gaofen 02	0,75 – 3	M	4	Chang Guang Satellite	China	2019
Jilin-1 Gaofen-03	1 – 4	M, V	64	Chang Guang Satellite	China	2019
Jilin-1 Gaofen-04	-	-	1	Chang Guang Satellite	China	2022
Jilin-1 Gaofen-06	-	-	30	Chang Guang Satellite	China	2023
Jilin-1 Guanpu	5	H	2	Chang Guang Satellite	China	2019
Jilin-1 Hongwai	-	T	8	Chang Guang Satellite	China	2022
Jilin-1 Kuanfu-02	0,5	M (wide swath)	1	Chang Guang Satellite	China	2023
Jilin-1 Mofang	< 1	M	4	Chang Guang Satellite	China	2022
Jilin-1 Pingtai	-	-	3	Chang Guang Satellite	China	2022
Jilin-1 Shipin	-	V	6	Chang Guang Satellite	China	2017
NuSat (NewSat)	0,7 – 4	M	38	Satellogic	USA	2016
Zhuhai-1 OHS	10	H	8	Zhuhai Orbita Aerospace Science & Technology	China	2018
Zhuhai-1 OVS	< 1,9	V	4	Zhuhai Orbita Aerospace Science & Technology	China	2017
Hyperfield	25	H	0 (100) ²	Kuva Space	Finland	2023
Tianyi	-	M	15	Spacety	China	2018
GRUS-1	2,5 – 5	M	5 (9)	Axelspace	Japan	2018
STORK	5	-	5 (14)	SatRev	Poland	2022
Jinzijing (Golden Bauhinia)	4	-	9 (132)	Beijing Zero G Lab	China	2021
Pleiades Neo	0,3 – 1,2	M	4 (?)	Airbus Intelligence	Germany	2021
GHOSt	8	H	3 (6)	Orbital Sidekick	USA	2023
Constellr	30	T	0 (30)	Constellr	Germany	2024
Sejong	5	M (VNIR) ³	1 (50)	Hancom Inspace	South Korea	2022
FOREST	80	T	2 (100)	OroraTech	Germany	2022
Pixxel	10	H	2 (20)	Pixxel	India	2022
EOS SAT	1,4 – 2,8	M	1 (7)	EOS Data Analytics	USA	2023

Name	Resolution, m	Bands	Number	Company	Country	Year
OpenConstellation	2,5	M	1 (25)	Open Cosmos	UK	2023
Wyvern	5,3	H	2 (36)	Wyvern	Canada	2023
Tanager (Carbon Mapper)	30	H	0 (2)	Planet Labs	USA	2023
EarthDaily	-	M	0 (8)	EarthDaily Analytics	Canada	2024
Esper	6	H	0 (18)	Esper Satellite Imagery	Australia	2023
Hydrosat	-	T	1 (16)	Hydrosat	USA	2023
Hypersat	9	H	0 (6)	Hypersat	USA	2023
HySpecIQ	-	H	0 (12)	HySpecIQ	USA	2023
Pelican	0,3	M	0 (32)	Planet Labs	USA	2023
JAPETUS	1 (M), 5 (H)	M, H	0 (20)	Prométhée Earth Intelligence	France	2023
GenMat	5	H (VNIR)	0 (600)	GenMat	Canada	2023
HotSat	3,5	T (MIR) ⁴ , V	1 (8)	SatVu	UK	2023
SatSure	1 – ?	M	0 (4)	SatSure	India	2024
XCraft	2	H, V	0 (12)	Xplore	USA	2023
Guardian	-	M, T	1 (20)	Aistech	Spain	2022
Capella-2 (Sequoia, Whitney)	1,2	X	9	Capella Space	USA	2020
Capella-3 (Acadia)	-	X	1	Capella Space	USA	2023
ICEYE	3	X	20	ICEYE	Finland	2018
Spacety (Chaohu)	1	X, C	2 (?)	Spacety	China	2022
QPS-SAR	< 0,5 (Spotlight)	X	3 (36)	iQPS	Japan	2019
StriX	3	X	1 (25)	Synspective	Japan	2022
Umbra-SAR	< 0,5	X	6 (24)	Umbra Lab	USA	2021
PIESAT	0,5 (Spotlight)	X	4	Galaxy Space	China	2023
XpressSAR	3	X	0 (4)	XpressSAR	USA	2024

¹ Spatial resolution in panchromatic and multispectral modes, respectively.

² Number of satellites in the constellation: current (planned).

³ Multispectral and hyperspectral imaging is typically performed in the wavelength range of 400–2500 nm. In this constellation, the wavelength range is limited to VNIR (visible and near-infrared): 400–1100 nm.

⁴ The thermal infrared band is limited to wavelengths of 8000–14000 nm. The satellite is imaging in the mid-wave infrared (MIR) band: 3400–5000 nm.